

Corona: Living or Non-Living? Yet Lessons for the Living

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These days Corona has become a buzz word that shocks and terrifies the whole world. By December 2019, China officially declared that a new type of Corona virus is attacking its State, Wuhan. The earlier one, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS 2), and the present Covid-19 belong to the group of Corona virus. First let us have a few basics of Virus in general and then go the lessons that humanity can get from it.

Corona: The Basics

Virus is extremely tiny and it is invisible to the naked eyes. These are the infectious agents with living and non-living features. The unique feature of a virus is that it can infect by entering a host cell; they cannot reproduce on their own. Viruses are not cells, they are strands of genetic material, with a protective protein coat called capsid. They infect a wide variety of organisms. Corona is said to be a large virus at the dimension of 20 to 400 nm. [A nano metre is 10^{-9} metre]. It has only RNA, covered by fat and protein. They get washed away by alcohol or soap (in 20 seconds); there are sort of spikes around its body, enabling it to get hooked onto another living cell; this gives the appearance of a crown, and that is how it gets its name, CORONA, which, in Latin, means a crown. When it enters our throat, it gets into the tissues there and gets multiplied very fast; at a particular stage it causes severe cough; the immune system

in our body fights against it by raising the body's temperature very high, in order to kill it. Whenever any foreign organism (like a virus or bacteria) enters our body, our immune system recognizes it in two ways: by the shape of the foreign agent and the chemicals emitted by it. White blood cells send Macrophages and Neutrophils to finish off those viruses. If they don't completely succeed and the virus has spread further in our body, lymphocytes, that is, T-cells which are part of them, try to cause the affected cells of the lungs to commit 'suicide' and to expel them so that they don't further damage other tissues; it also tries to reduce the number of cells that are engulfed by the virus. If the virus is still invincible, B-Cells, which is a lymphocyte, try to tackle the virus; these cells recognize the virus and drag them to lymph nodes and kill it with the chemicals produced over there. Similarly, Corona virus, after a few days of stay at the throat, enters lungs through the respiratory tracts; the inner walls of lungs have billions of very minute Epithelial cells; virus enters these cells and sends its RNA and this multiplies into millions, and each RNA will turn into a virus! Within ten days or so, most part of the lungs will be engulfed by the virus.

When our immune system sends cells into the lungs to fight against the virus, a sad and horrible thing happens – virus enters these fighter-cells of the immune system to kill them; further they create a “confusion” in the genes of those cells. The cells of our immune system usually communicate with one another with the help a

chemical called, Cytokines. The affected cells send out confusing cytokines and the neutrophils cells, which actually come in to save lungs, begin to destroy immune system cells, instead of killing the virus. Similarly, T-cells,

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instead of doing its actual job, begin to give out information to destroy the healthy cells in lungs. With this, being vulnerable to further attacks by bacteria, lungs develop pneumonia; and this very often becomes fatal to the patients.

Thus, Corona is extremely devilish in making our own immune system antagonistic to our body (so it looks like, even God cannot help us!). Even the T-killer cells and B-cells have not succeeded in identifying the killer corona exactly,

because the virus has millions of ways to create the communicating-chemical, cytokines, and that is why, we are not able to arrest the multiplication of the virus and we cannot make a vaccine to prevent it either. When we normally take medicines, they usually change into chemical information and fight against the virus or bacteria directly, or enable our immune system to produce the required antibodies to fight against them. But as Corona takes our immune system into its control, the medical world is really stunned and unable to fight against this killer virus, corona. The good soldiers, T- and B-cells, are so badly misled and confused that they begin to destroy the good cells in lungs, instead of saving them. But in spite of all these difficulties, our immune system is largely able to fight against the corona virus, though, who already have respiratory issues or

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low immune system are easily affected, even resulting in unfortunate deaths. The diabetic patients have less immunity power; those with heart diseases or hyper tension are not able to circulate enough blood to fight against this virus. But if these problems are controlled with proper medications and with sufficient physical exercises, they also can escape the virus attack.

We don't unfortunately know how long it will take to develop a vaccine to prevent it because even for HIV, we have not been able to invent a vaccine, even after 35 years! Though HIV also cripples our immune system, it luckily does not spread through coughs and sneezes, and at that perspective the present Corona is more dangerous than HIV. However, luckily, a lot of Corona-infected patients do recover from it, if their immune system is strong enough. As we don't have the medicines to cure, nor any vaccine to prevent it, the best way is to be very cautious not to contract this virus. Several precautionary measures are taken individually and collectively to personally escape from it and not to contribute to the transmission of it. [Something interesting to think about: **V _ R _ S** What is missing?... I and U... So, only **U** and **I** can kill the virus, by keeping ourselves away, and, in fact, we can give VRS (Voluntary Retirement from Service) to the virus!]

Corona's Lasting Lessons: Life Still as Mystery!

The Corona-related issues, in my opinion, give one more occasion to reflect upon the very notion of life and its meaning and meaningfulness. Perhaps we can never understand what (human) life is, as long as we are "caught" up in the contours of life; we may have to soar up, or go 'beyond' life, so to say, to understand what life is and that is never possible. If one is able to do that perhaps one

Are Viruses Living or Non-living?

Characteristics of life	Virus	Cell
Growth	No	Yes
Homeostasis	No	Yes
Metabolism	No	Yes
Mutation	Yes	Yes
Nucleic Acid	DNA or RNA	DNA
Reproduction	Only with host	Cell Division

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cannot communicate to others about it, as others are still entangled in the web of life!

T. D. Singh, a pioneer in *Science-Religion Dialogue* from the Indian thought perspectives, suggests, "A sincere attempt to understand life... is of foundational importance and it will have important relevance in deciding the relation between science and religion." Erwin Schrodinger, a quantum physicist wonders, in his book, *What is Life?* (1944). *Science Journal* (July 2005) lists out 125 questions which cannot be answered by modern science; for instance, 'How and where did life on earth arise?' – and still more intriguing question is, 'What is that life?', Albert Szent-Gyorgyi, a Hungarian Nobel Laureate and biochemist declares, "In my search for the secret of life, I ended up with atoms and electrons, which have no life at all. Somewhere along the line, life has run out through my fingers".

Sciences may be able to separate all biochemicals like nucleic acids (RNA, DNA), carbohydrates, lipids, enzymes and all other basic building blocks of organic bodies but will they ever discover what is that which gives life to them? It is said that more than fifty minerals, salts and chemicals are essential for life and the ratio of their combination is also very crucial for the holistic health of our body; for instance, if sodium is more, it damages blood vessels and increases blood pressure and causes other heart diseases; but if it is less, it causes low blood pressure, damages nerve cells, the muscles of the heart and digestive systems. The most fascinating fact is that all these chemicals are "lifeless" in themselves, but still they are necessary to make life possible!

It is generally understood that a **living being** is made up of cellular organization; it needs nutrition, respiration; it grows and develops, moves, reproduces, responds to stimuli; further it maintains homeostasis, stability and constant internal conditions; metabolism takes place in it; having organ systems

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to carry out different functions of the being. **A non-living being** is made up of atoms and sub-atomic particles; it does not need food for energy to perform activities; it does not grow in size or develop into something else; it does not eat or excrete, nor reproduce or multiply. **A dead being** is an organism that once had life, but now no pulse; eyes are dilated, body is cold, emitting foul odour, muscles become rigid and start decomposing. Further, in the medical world, two types of death are recognized: **Somatic Death** – it involves stoppage of respiration, circulation of blood and brain functions, and **Molecular Death** – involves the death of all organs, at different times; while liver dies rapidly, heart takes sixty minutes and cornea takes six hours to die. There is obviously a time-gap between these two types of death; all living beings will undergo these two types death.

But regarding the status of virus there is an alarming ambiguity! One cannot easily decide whether it is a living or a non-living being. It manifests some signs of life like multiplying when it is parasitic to another living cell (of a plant/animal), but left alone in the environment it cannot respond to stimuli, it assumes a crystalline form, cannot grow or multiply or reproduce. Outside a living cell it cannot survive, because it cannot create energy and there is no ‘agency’ to reach out to food, nor is there any metabolism (unlike bacteria, amoebas); some scientists consider virus as a missing link between non-life and life.

That is why, even today, the notion of life and its origin are very mysterious. Werner Arber, a renowned biologist makes an honest confession: “I must confess that I don’t understand how life came about... The most primitive cell may require at least several hundred

different specific biological micro-molecules. How such already quite complex structure may have come together,

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remains a mystery to me. The possibility of the existence of a creator, of God, represents to me a satisfactory solution to this problem”.

Equality: An Indisputable Fact

Humans are now forced by the corona to feel equal to one another. Though every nation and every race has been focusing on the differences to show its might over the others, to boss over others and to manipulate all possible ways to safeguard its own comfort zones, yet they are now taught a great lesson of equality, perhaps, in a tough way! The virus does not know the differences of regions or religions, colour or creed, rich or poor, wise or otherwise; it does not discriminate against the developed or developing countries. Not only ordinary people on the streets are killed but also even those from the royal families are also not spared (like the Princess of Spain). After several centuries the rich and the affluent are taught to remind themselves of life’s transience and fragility. Many of us have been living as if youth, health and wealth are the default settings of life, but now we are taught some basic lessons of life, perhaps in a harsh way! The whole world joins together in fighting against the menace; all leading scientists and research laboratories all over the world join their hands to find out the ways and means to control the spread of the infection, and to find a vaccine against it.

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Every nation or race may have unique achievements and capacities but to the eyes of nature we all are same and equal. All natural forces are equally harsh or equally gentle to all humans, without any discrimination on any account. Of course, we need to cherish the differences of various regions, languages, creeds and cultures, but we must not forget the indisputable fact that we are all basically equal, travelling in the same boat in the vast ocean of reality; as Pope Francis, in the context of corona-issues, reminds us that “all of us are fragile

and disoriented, but at the same time important and needed, all of us called to row together”. Instead of focusing on the differences that keep us apart, we are now taught to focus on the factors that unite us, realizing that we are certainly equal.

Humility: A Natural Emotion for any Thinking Person

Corona, such a tiny and mysterious thing poses an indomitable challenge to the world of science. In fact, science has even measured the unimaginably huge universe; it has managed to learn that the invisible universe is much larger than the visible one (the former is 150 sextillions – 150×10^{21} times bigger than the latter!); however we become so helpless that we have, so to say, to surrender to this little virus. Even the developed countries feel very abandoned and overwhelmed in dealing with this menace; they just throw their hands up in total surrender. Glorious economic powers and mighty military prowess don't make any sense to this invisible agent. Is it another instance to show that the *invisible determines the visible*?¹

This small little thing has made the whole world to come to a standstill; it has closed the worship places down; it has silenced the noises of the ultra-modern world; it has caused the downfall of the economy; transports have been halted. Yes, it is a big blow to humanity, which has been assuming that it is in control of everything, including its own destiny. But humanity is now forced to look for wisdom and discernment to find out what the real fulfilment in life is; it is time to listen to the *INNER VOICE*; perhaps, we can now hear it very loudly as the external noise is forced to be silent. Even a cursory look at this scenario teaches a

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person, and every nation, to be humble, no matter what his/her/its achievements are!

Conclusion

It is also time to think of God's innumerable blessings. It is said that an eighty-year-old man was infected by corona; fortunately, he got recovered in a few days; he was discharged from the ICU. The hospital gave him the bill to pay the amount of 5000 Euro for the ventilator he used. Seeing the bill, he started weeping bitterly; the staff asked him, whether he had no that much of money to pay. In-between the sobbing he said, "No, no, I have the money... I just thought that all these eighty years I have been breathing so effortlessly, but I never thanked God for such a precious gift, that he gave me completely free!". Yes, that makes us realize how humble we need to feel, for all the sun, water and air that we have been enjoying from nature without any payment!

Finally, this dangerous virus may be living or non-living, but it certainly has lessons for us, who are still living. As we are all existentially connected, we can't survive as an individual nation or race; let us unite together; let us all, individually and collectively, do whatever we can to fight against this virus and save the earth for the future generations. Brains and knees (efforts and prayers) have to complement each other because what one can do, the other cannot do. Let us raise our hands and hearts to the "SKY". Let us do our best, trusting the capacity of the God-given reasoning power.

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¹ As sciences develop humanity is increasingly realizing that the visible world is determined by the invisible, in all possible worlds; for instance, the physical world is determined by the four invisible fundamental physical forces, both at the sub-atomic and cosmic levels; the galaxies in the incredibly vast dark universe are determined by the invisible black holes, and even our very words and actions of our day-to-day lives are determined (or shaped) by the invisible emotions, convictions, beliefs and value-systems.